

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

Dear Reviewers, We thank all the reviewers for their insightful and valuable comments. Hereinafter, some results concerned by the reviewers are discussed below. Hope that we could make ourselves better understood and the confusions resolved.

1. Other Factors of The Offloading Model

Fig. 20. Performance of IOTPIM with and without considering compute time

Compute Time: In our evaluation, the frequency used for the CPU is 2.5 GHZ, while the frequency of the PIM cores we keep the same with DRAM, DDR2400 MHZ is the DRAM equivalent frequency and the actual operating frequency is 1200 MHZ. The compute time of the CPU and PIM logic are not the same. To evaluate the impact of compute time in offloading model, Figure 20 shows the speedup without and with considering compute time (IOTPIM-w-CT). Even with considering compute time, both IOTPIM and IOTPIM-w-CT still achieve the same speedup. This is because, for data-intensive applications, the performance is bounded by memory access. In addition, the memory accesses of CPU and PIM logic have a wide discrepancy.

Fig. 21. Performance of IOTPIM with and without considering the usage of core or shared resources

Usage of Core or Shared Resources: To analyse the impact of overall system usage of cores and other shared resources on the offloading model, Figure 21 shows the speedup of IOTPIM with or without considering overall system usage of cores (IOTPIM-w-UC) and the shared resources (IOTPIM-w-SR). IOTPIM-w-UC prioritizes offloading PIM instructions for busy cores, while other cores execute on their own. IOTPIM-w-SR considers on-chip LLC shared resources, and cannot offload PIM instructions if there has free resources, allowing these PIM instructions to use the shared resources. We observe that IOTPIM-w-UC and IOTPIM-w-SR instead cause performance degradation of 13.13%, 5.77% compared to IOTPIM. This is because the performance of PIM instruction is dominated by memory accesses and is not sensitive to the usage of cores or other shared resources. Directly offloading these PIM instructions instead allows them to have efficient memory access and does not take up valuable shared resources.

Fig. 22. The offloading accuracy of different cache hierarchy with different cache size

2. Generality

Various Cache Configuration: To analyze the generality of IOTPIM for different cache hierarchies and cache sizes, Figure 22 shows the offloading accuracy for three types of modern cache hierarchies. Two-level (L1: 64KB, L2: 8MB) like Intel-Kentsfield XE⁴; three-level (L1: 32KB, L2: 512KB, L3: 16MB) like AMD Zen 2 microarchitecture⁵; four-level (L1: 64KBL2: 256KBL3: 6MBL4: 128MB) like Intel Broadwell microarchitecture⁶. These cache hierarchies can cover various types of cache configuration. Our IOTPIM still achieves high accuracy for different cache hierarchies two-level, three-level, and four-level by 90.91%,92.27%,91.03%, respectively. Note that the cache size is also different for different cache hierarchies. This shows that our IOTPIM can work under different ache hierarchies and cache sizes.

Fig. 23. The offloading accuracy of the three level cache hierarchy using different latencies

Different Cache Latencies: To evaluate the impact of cache latencies, we analyze the three-level cache hierarchy using different latencies. Figure 23 shows the offloading accuracy of three-level cache hierarchy using three different type latencies: type1 (4, 7, 27 cycles); type2 (6, 12, 31 cycles); type3 (10,18, 40 cycles). IOTPIM still has high offload accuracy by 91.98%, 91.16%, 91.54%, respectively. This shows that IOTPIM also has generality in terms of different cache latencies.

Fig. 24. The offloading accuracy of different PIM architectures

Different PIM Architectures: The 3D stacked PIM architecture is another general-purpose PIM architecture by integrating compute logic. Figure 24 shows the offloading accuracy when using the DIMM-level PIM architecture and the 3D stacked PIM architecture. IOTPIM achieves almost the same offloading accuracy of 91.89%, 91.41%, respectively.

⁴<https://ark.intel.com/content/www/us/en/ark/products/codename/23489/products-formerly-kentsfield.html>

⁵<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Zen2>

⁶[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Broadwell_\(microarchitecture\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Broadwell_(microarchitecture))

This shows the generality of IOTPIM across different general-purpose PIM architectures.

3. Fair comparison

Fig. 25. Performance of IOTPIM against the baseline and four state-of-the-art PIM offloading techniques

Fig. 26. Energy consumptions of IOTPIM against the baseline and four state-of-the-art PIM offloading techniques

Figure 25 and Figure 26 show a fair comparison with other offloading techniques, both TDO-CIM and PRIMO using their specialized PIM architecture. IOTPIM on average outperforms TDO-CIM by $1.34\times$ on performance and $1.22\times$ on energy saving. IOTPIM also on average outperforms PRIMO by $1.28\times$ on performance and $1.42\times$ on energy saving.

4. Instruction Offloading

Fig. 27. The number of offloading instructions of four state-of-the-art PIM offloading techniques

Figure 27 shows the number of offloading instructions for these PIM offloading techniques. Because the number of offloading instructions varies considerably from different applications, to better sense of scale between the different offloading techniques in the Figure 12, we select a representative part of the execution process. The blank spaces in the figure for specific techniques indicate that they have almost no instructions for offloading.

5. The Motivation of Prediction Model

Although the cache model is simple, obtaining the parameters for the model is complex and has a high overhead. First, the offloading decision for instructions must be determined at the compile time to generate the instruction binary for a fixed compute logic (before the application execution). We need to use the offloading model of the instruction to determine whether offloading can improve performance. However, the parameters (i.e., the number of hits in each memory level) of the offloading model are not known before the application

Fig. 28. Pre-run analysis time normalized to normal execution time

Fig. 29. Performance comparison between the baseline and IOTPIM with or without per-input analysis for GIN

execution. We must pre-run the application for analysis to collect these parameters of the offloading model. Second, the pre-run overhead is very high compared to the normal execution time of the application. Figure 1 shows the pre-run analysis time overhead over the normal execution of the application. The pre-run analysis overhead is $11.62\times$ the normal execution of the application. This is because we need to record the number of hits in each memory level for the instructions at pre-run time.

Third, different input datasets may have different data locality on cache for the same instruction. Instruction offloading decision is inaccurate, if it is decided for all input datasets only by pre-run analysis for the application with a given input dataset. Figure 29 depicts the performance results for the *Graph Isomorphism Networks (GIN)* application with the one-time pre-run analysis on *Arxiv* dataset and a per-input pre-run analysis. We observe that the offloading decision cannot be shared between different input datasets. The offloading decision with only pre-run once shares the same analysis results for all input datasets, but causes the performance degradation for some input datasets. For instance, *Cora* has 41.22% performance loss. In contrast, the per-input pre-run analysis improves the performance of the application with the accurate decision, but it introduces expensive pre-run analysis overhead.

In summary, the benefits of PIM are eliminated by the costly overhead of the pre-run analysis on each dataset for application. To mitigate the expensive overhead of the per-input pre-run analysis, a prediction model is necessary. We would like to predict (rather than pre-run analysis) the offloading decision accurately as if the per-input pre-run analysis were performed.